

Centrifugal and Tidal Break Up of a Sun like Star

In the Presence of a Compact Companion

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Abstract

This paper presents theoretical calculations for the critical rotational velocity at which the stellar matter will start breaking - up for the three layers of the Sun (Core, Radiation Zone, and Photosphere). We also study the effect of the rotational velocity on the hypothetical critical distance of the Sun from a compact star (2 Solar Mass Neutron Star). The calculations involve a force balance equation between the Gravitational Force on one side and Gas Pressure, Centrifugal Force, and Radiation Pressure on the other side. The calculations on Gas Pressure uses the Polytropic model of the Sun which is considered an $n = 3$ star by the Eddington Standard Model of Stellar Structure. The calculation can be applied to other stars knowing the density profiles and standard numerical data. It is to be noted that our calculations utilise only the standard numerical data without the use of calculus to obtain the approximate values in this paper. The upper limit for rotational velocities for the different layers are found to lie in the range of 200 km s^{-1} - 350 km s^{-1} . We observe that the radiation pressure plays a negligible role in influencing the critical rotational velocities of matter in all three layers of the Sun. We also find that the critical rotational velocity of the inner layers is smaller in magnitude than for the outer layers. Our calculations also show that the distance from the Sun at which solar matter will start flying - off the surface, in the presence of a compact companion, increases as the rotational velocity of the Sun increases and this critical distance is of the order of the Solar Radii.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Sun has been an object of interest for centuries and continues to be the most observed star. Extensive studies have been conducted in order to primarily develop a stellar model that effectively describes the physical properties, energy transport mechanisms, and stability of a stellar system. The central work in this respect has been the development of the Standard Solar Model which is a mathematical treatment of the Sun as a spherical ball of gas in varying states of ionisation such that the hydrogen in the deep interior exists as completely ionised plasma. The Standard Solar Model has described stellar structure through differential equations derived from fundamental physical principles. The model is also constrained by boundary conditions such as luminosity, radius, age and composition of the Sun. An interesting question that can be investigated utilising the Standard Solar Model is what the critical velocity would be for different layers of the Sun before matter starts to break up and escape. These critical velocities can be further utilised to study the stability of the Sun in the presence of a hypothetical Compact star. In a broader context, the methodology of the calculation can be applied to simple astrophysical binary systems to study the critical stability conditions. This paper presents the theoretical calculations on these very aspects. Three layers of the Sun are considered in the calculations presented: Core, Radiation Zone, and Photosphere. To begin with a general idea, a very crude calculation can be performed to identify the range to be adhered to in the calculations presented later in the paper. This crude calculation can be performed directly by balancing Centrifugal Force against Gravitational Force without gas and radiation pressure considerations as -

$$dmR_{\odot}\omega^2 = \frac{GM_{\odot} dm}{R_{\odot}^2}$$

Substituting $G = 6.67 \times 10^{-11} \text{ Nm}^2 \text{ kg}^{-2}$, $M_{\odot} = 2 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}$, and $R_{\odot} = 7 \times 10^8 \text{ m}$ and then solving for ω , we get $\omega \approx 6.24 \times 10^{-4} \text{ rad s}^{-1}$. This translates to a rotational velocity of $v \approx 436.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ using the equation $v = r\omega$. This is a limiting assumption that has been used to check the correctness of future calculations. The correct estimate is obtained by considering Gas Pressure calculated using the Polytropic equation of state for an $n = 3$ star, radiation pressure calculated as intensity over speed of light, and equations relating to the solution of the Lane – Emden equation, which reads as –

$$\frac{1}{\xi^2} \frac{d}{d\xi} \left(\xi^2 \frac{d\theta}{d\xi} \right) + \theta^n = 0$$

Where ξ is a dimensionless radius and θ is related to density ρ , and thus pressure, for central density ρ_c by –

$$\rho = \rho_c \theta^n$$

The velocities obtained for each of the mentioned layers are then applied hypothetically as the velocity of the Sun to calculate the critical distance at which imbalance in forces caused by the strong tidal force of an imaginary Compact star would start breaking up solar matter at the surface.

2. CALCULATIONS

Force Balance Equation

Figure 1 - Depiction of the various forces acting on surface layer mass dm (shown in red).

Based on figure 1, the force balance equation for any layer of the Sun can be written as a sum of the forces due to gas pressure (F_{Gas}), centrifugal force (F_c), and the radiation pressure (F_{rad}) balancing the gravitational force (F_{Grav}) -

$$F_{Gas} + F_c + F_{rad} = F_{Grav}$$

Which is expanded as,

$$PdA + dmR\omega^2 + P_{rad}dA = \frac{GM dm}{R^2} \quad - (1)$$

Where, P is the internal gas pressure, dm is a small element of mass, dA is the surface area of dm , R is distance of dm from centre of the Sun (for surface dm , R is radius of the Sun), ω is the Angular velocity of the Sun, G is the Universal Gravitational Constant, and M is the mass of the Sun enclosed within the sphere of radius R . Now, $dm = \rho dV = \rho dA dr$, where ρ is the

local density of the layer where dm is situated and dr is the thickness of the layer under consideration. Substituting this and rearranging the above equation to obtain ω , we get,

$$\omega = \sqrt{\frac{GM\rho dr - PR^2}{\rho R^3 dr} - \frac{P_{rad}}{\rho dr R}} \quad - (2)$$

Gas Pressure Calculation

The Polytopic Equation of State can be written as,

$$P = k\rho^{\frac{n+1}{n}} \quad - (3)$$

Where,

$$k = \frac{4\pi GR^2 \rho_c^{\frac{n-1}{n}}}{(n+1)\xi^2} \quad - (4)$$

Substituting (4) in (3) and $n = 3$ (for Solar - mass main sequence stars), we get,

$$P = \frac{\pi GR^2 \rho_c^{\frac{2}{3}}}{\xi^2} \rho^{\frac{4}{3}} \quad - (5)$$

Where, ρ_c is the density of the centre of the Sun, R and ρ have the standard meanings as mentioned earlier, and ξ is the rescaled R using a constant α as -

$$\xi = \frac{R}{\alpha}$$

Figure 2 - Graphical solutions to the Lane - Emden Equation for different values of Polytopic index n . Here θ is a quantity related to the variation in density as $\rho = \rho_c \theta^n$.

Radiation Pressure Calculation

The numerical value of radiation pressure for a given surface is calculated as –

$$P_{\text{rad}} = \frac{4\sigma T^4}{3c} \quad - (6)$$

Where, σ is the Stefan – Boltzmann Constant equal to $5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-4}$, c is the speed of light equal to $3 \times 10^8 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, and T is the temperature of the layer under consideration.

Photosphere

The photosphere is the first outer surface layer of the Sun. The magnitude of its distance from the centre of the Sun is approximately equal to the radius of the Sun. The local density ρ of the Photosphere is about $10^{-6} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, dr is the thickness of the Photosphere and is about 500 km, the central density ρ_c is about $1.6 \times 10^5 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, and M is the mass enclosed and is equal to the mass of the sun. According to the Lane – Emden solution, for boundary condition (Here Photosphere is the boundary of the Sun), $\theta(\zeta) = 0$. On observing the plot (figure 2) of $\theta(\zeta)$ vs ζ for an $n = 3$ star, we see that the required solution is $\zeta = 6.89$. Substituting these values along with the standard constants in equation (5), we get $P \approx 63.8 \text{ Pa}$. Now, the temperature T of the photosphere is approximately 5777 K. Substituting this in equation (6) along with the necessary constants, we get $P_{\text{rad}} = 0.28 \text{ Pa}$. Substituting all the required values in equation (2), we obtain the following values:

$$\frac{GM\rho dr - PR^2}{\rho R^3 dr} \approx 2.07 \times 10^{-7} \text{ rad}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$$

$$\frac{P_{\text{rad}}}{\rho dr R} \approx 8.0 \times 10^{-10} \text{ rad}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$$

Here, the radiation pressure term is about two orders of magnitude smaller than the gas pressure term and hence can be neglected. Taking the square root of the gas pressure term, we get $\omega = 4.55 \times 10^{-4} \text{ rad s}^{-1}$. This translates to a rotational velocity of $v \approx 318.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ using the equation $v = r\omega$, where $r = R_{\odot}$.

Radiation Zone

The radiation zone is the second of the inner layers of the Sun extending from $0.25R_{\odot}$ to $0.6R_{\odot}$ and hence the R to be used in the equations is $0.6R_{\odot}$. The local density ρ is about $1.01 \times 10^4 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, the central density ρ_c is about $1.6 \times 10^5 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, and the thickness dr is about $3 \times 10^8 \text{ m}$. Mass of the sphere enclosed by the Radiation Zone is calculated as $M = \rho V$, where $V = \frac{4}{3}\pi d^3$, (where $d = 0.35R$). This mass is added to the mass of the core which is about 10^{30} kg to yield a total mass $M = 1.622 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}$. Now, using the equation $\xi = \frac{R}{\alpha}$ and

the fact that α is constant, the required ζ value can be calculated from the known boundary condition value as $\zeta = 0.6 \times 6.89 \approx 4.13$. Substituting the required values in equation (5) gives the value of $P = 1.39 \times 10^{15}$ Pa. The temperature T of the radiation zone is about 4.5 million K. Substituting this in equation (6) yields $P_{\text{rad}} = 1.03 \times 10^{11}$ Pa. Finally, substituting all the required values in equation (2), we obtain the following values:

$$\frac{GM\rho dr - PR^2}{\rho R^3 dr} \approx 3.68 \times 10^{-7} \text{ rad}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$$

$$\frac{P_{\text{rad}}}{\rho dr R} \approx 8.09 \times 10^{-11} \text{ rad}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$$

Here, the radiation pressure term is smaller than the gas pressure term by three orders of magnitude and hence can be neglected. Taking the square root of the remaining value we get $\omega = 6.07 \times 10^{-4} \text{ rad s}^{-1}$. This translates to a rotational velocity of $v \approx 255 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ using the equation $v = r\omega$, where $r = 0.6R_{\odot}$.

Core

The core forms the innermost layer of the Sun. It extends to a distance of $0.25R_{\odot}$ from the centre of the Sun and has an average density $\rho = 8.5 \times 10^4 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The thickness of the core $dr = 1.5 \times 10^8 \text{ m}$, the central density ρ_c is about $1.6 \times 10^5 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, and its mass $M = 10^{30} \text{ kg}$. Now, using the equation $\xi = \frac{R}{\alpha}$ and the fact that α is constant, the required ζ value can be calculated from the boundary condition value as $\zeta = 0.25 \times 6.89 \approx 1.723$. Substituting the required values in equation (5) gives the value of $P = 2.38 \times 10^{16}$ Pa. The temperature of the core of the Sun is about 15 million K. Substituting this in equation (6) yields $P_{\text{rad}} = 1.28 \times 10^{13}$ Pa. Finally, substituting all the required values in equation (2), we obtain the following values:

$$\frac{GM\rho dr - PR^2}{\rho R^3 dr} \approx 1.78 \times 10^{-6} \text{ rad}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$$

$$\frac{P_{\text{rad}}}{\rho dr R} \approx 5.74 \times 10^{-9} \text{ rad}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$$

Here, the radiation pressure term is smaller than the gas pressure term by two orders of magnitude and hence can be neglected. Taking the square root of the remaining value we get $\omega = 1.33 \times 10^{-3} \text{ rad s}^{-1}$. This translates to a rotational velocity of $v \approx 233.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ using the equation $v = r\omega$, where $r = 0.25R_{\odot}$.

Figure 3 - Depicts the critical velocities at which matter would break - up in the different layers of the Sun

Limiting distance from a Compact Star

Hypothetically assuming the existence of a 2 Solar Mass Neutron Star in the vicinity of the Sun, the limiting distance at which matter in the star would start to break up can be calculated considering tidal force effects in addition to forces considered in the previous calculations. This limiting distance in which the Sun, held together only by its own gravity, will disintegrate due to the Neutron Star's tidal forces exceeding the Sun's gravitational self-attraction is defined as the Roche limit of the Sun. The calculation has been performed for three cases of rotational velocity of the Sun-like star – 2 km s^{-1} , 233.5 km s^{-1} , and 255 km s^{-1} , as calculated in the cases above. (The case involving a rotational velocity of 318.5 km s^{-1} would mean surface break – up due to rotation alone and would give an infinite distance if substituted in the formula derived below).

Force Balance Equation for Compact Star Calculations

Figure 4 - Depiction of a two-star system comprising of the Sun and a Compact Star and the forces acting on the Sun's surface mass dm (shown in red). Roche Lobes are teardrop shaped regions bounded by a critical gravitation equipotential within which an orbiting material is bound to the star. In this case the Roche Lobes are arranged such that surface matter of the Sun is just outside the Roche Lobe of the Compact Star.

Based on figure 4, the force balance equation can be written as –

$$F_{Gas} + F_c + F_{tidal} = F_{Grav}$$

Which is expanded as,

$$PdA + dmR_{\odot}\omega^2 + \frac{2G(2M_{\odot})R_{\odot} dm}{d^3} = \frac{GM dm}{R_{\odot}^2} \quad - (7)$$

Where, P is the internal gas pressure, dm is small element of mass, dA is surface area of dm , R_{\odot} is radius of the Sun, ω is the Angular velocity of the Sun, G is the Universal Gravitational Constant, M_{\odot} is the interior mass of the Sun, and d is the required Roche limit. Now, $dm = \rho dV = \rho dA dr$, where ρ is the local density of the layer where dm is situated. Substituting this and rearranging the above equation to obtain d , we get,

$$d = \left(\frac{4GM_{\odot}R_{\odot}^3 \rho dr}{GM_{\odot}\rho dr - \rho dr \omega^2 R_{\odot}^3 - PR_{\odot}^2} \right)^{1/3} \quad - (8)$$

We know that $v = r\omega$. Thus,

$$\omega^2 = \frac{v^2}{r^2} \quad - (9)$$

Case I ($v = 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$)

Substituting $v = 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $r = R_{\odot} = 7 \times 10^8 \text{ m}$ in equation (9), we get $\omega = 2.86 \times 10^{-6} \text{ rad s}^{-1}$. Substituting this value of ω and the values of the constants as per surface conditions $G = 6.67 \times 10^{-11} \text{ Nm}^2 \text{ kg}^{-2}$, $M_{\odot} = 2 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}$, $R_{\odot} = 7 \times 10^8 \text{ m}$, $\rho = 10^{-6} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, $dr = 500$

km, $P = 63.8$ Pa (As calculated for the photosphere previously) in equation (8), we get, $d = 1.96R_{\odot}$.

Case II ($v = 233.5$ km s⁻¹)

Substituting $v = 233.5$ km s⁻¹ and $r = R_{\odot} = 7 \times 10^8$ m in equation (9), we get $\omega = 3.34 \times 10^{-4}$ rad s⁻¹. Substituting this value of ω and the values of the constants as per surface conditions $G = 6.67 \times 10^{-11}$ Nm² kg⁻², $M_{\odot} = 2 \times 10^{30}$ kg, $R_{\odot} = 7 \times 10^8$ m, $\rho = 10^{-6}$ kg m⁻³, $dr = 500$ km, $P = 63.8$ Pa (As calculated for the photosphere previously) in equation (8), we get, $d = 2.54R_{\odot}$.

Case III ($v = 255$ km s⁻¹)

Substituting $v = 255$ km s⁻¹ and $r = R_{\odot} = 7 \times 10^8$ m in equation (9), we get $\omega = 3.64 \times 10^{-4}$ rad s⁻¹. Substituting this value of ω and the values of the constants as per surface conditions $G = 6.67 \times 10^{-11}$ Nm² kg⁻², $M_{\odot} = 2 \times 10^{30}$ kg, $R_{\odot} = 7 \times 10^8$ m, $\rho = 10^{-6}$ kg m⁻³, $dr = 500$ km, $P = 63.8$ Pa (As calculated for the photosphere previously) in equation (8), we get, $d = 2.76R_{\odot}$.

A similar calculation can be performed for various different rotational velocities (50 km s⁻¹, 75 km s⁻¹, 100 km s⁻¹, 125 km s⁻¹, 150 km s⁻¹, 175 km s⁻¹, and 200 km s⁻¹) to obtain the following curve.

Figure 5 - Depicts the Roche limit in the presence of a 2 Solar Mass Neutron Star for various rotational velocities including the cases considered.

3. CONCLUSION

Through our calculations we have arrived at two trends. The critical velocity of a layer of the Sun at which the layer matter starts to break up increases from 233.5 km s^{-1} for the core to 255 km s^{-1} for the radiation zone and to 318.5 km s^{-1} for the photosphere. We observe a larger increase in critical velocity in moving from the radiation zone to the photosphere than in moving from the core to the radiation zone. This can be accounted for by the change in gas pressure. The respective contributions of gas pressure in the core and radiation zone differ by a smaller margin than that between the radiation zone and photosphere. As a result, a greater value of centrifugal force is necessary to cause a force imbalance for matter in the photosphere. We have also observed that the radiation pressure term is negligible in all three cases considered, even at temperatures as high as 15 million K. This negligibility can be attributed to the high density and layer thickness in the case of the core and radiation zone and to low surface temperature (5777 K) in the case of the photosphere. Next, the Roche limit of the Sun in the presence of a 2 Solar Mass companion star is also found to increase from $1.96R_{\odot}$ at the Sun's present velocity to $2.54R_{\odot}$ at $v = 233.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and further to $2.76R_{\odot}$ at $v = 255 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, as with increasing velocity, centrifugal force increases and less contribution is required from the tidal force to cause break – up of matter at the surface. From figure 5, it is observed that the value of d is found to change at a very slow rate (nearly constant) until $v = 125 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. This is because of the very small change in the value of the $\rho dr \omega^2 R_{\odot}^3$ term in the derived equation on approaching $v = 125 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ after which the differences in value of the above term become more significant.

REFERENCES

1. Lane, Jonathan Homer (1870). "On the Theoretical Temperature of the Sun under the Hypothesis of a Gaseous Mass Maintaining its Volume by its Internal Heat and Depending on the Laws of Gases Known to Terrestrial Experiment". *The American Journal of Science and Arts*. 2. 50: 57–74.
2. Horedt, G.P. (2004). *Polytropes. Applications in Astrophysics and Related Fields*, Dordrecht: Kluwer. ISBN 1-4020-2350-2
3. Shankar R., *Principles of Quantum Mechanics*, 2nd edition.
4. Carroll, Bradley W. & Dale A. Ostlie, *An Introduction to Modern Astrophysics*, 2nd edition.
5. Jackson, John David, (1999) *Classical Electrodynamics*.
6. Kardar, Mehran. "Statistical Physics of Particles".
7. Eric W. Weisstein (2007). "Eric Weisstein's World of Physics – Roche Limit"